

ADVERTISING AND HUMOR
IN THE MODERN GENERATION

by

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10459725

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

December 2023

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12/8/2023

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1/2/24

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Abstract

As young individuals aged 18-26 (Gen Z) have grown to become adult consumers, there is a question of how to appeal to them commercially. Their spending and buying habits have become the main focus of advertisers and companies. There is a growing need to grab their attention and understand why humor may entice them to buy their products. The need for more research on what humorous tactics appeal to Gen Z is a significant area of inquiry that has yet to be considered. With our online surveys only given to those within the Gen Z demographic via the internet, questions about current running advertisements, their opinions on those advertisements, and their interpretation of humor provided critical insight into a prospective population's general thoughts on the subject. Our findings indicate that, like other generations, humor is considerably effective, but specifically with Gen Z, their appeal to these tactics is entirely niche compared to past generations. The Gen Z market is more responsive to *absurd* tactics, which use humor that does not feel corporate-made and more avant-garde. Gen Z wants *creativity, authenticity, and relevance*. Companies and advertisers can use humor in a unique, non-traditional way to gain the appeal and recognition of the Gen Z market, cementing the demographics' loyalty and attention.

Introduction

Since its inception, the advertising industry has had the same idea: to figure out what will make its growing audience want and remember a specific product. Figuring out what the public responds to has always been challenging and will remain that way. Particular phrases, people, or appeals allow a product to find its place in the minds of specific consumers for years to come. It is impossible to please everyone, but some methods have been sworn to be tried and true for powerful brand positioning, such as humor. In research conducted by Cline & Kellaris (2007), their results concluded that “Humor strength and humor-message relatedness jointly influence participants' recall of advertising claims” (pg .64). There is a definite advantage of using humor as an appeal for advertising but when a specific demographic is involved, is that tactic still viable and successful? Gen Z, the demographic of individuals born between 1997 and 2012, is a fast-growing generation of consumers with unique interests, beliefs, and things they find humorous, yet the advertising industry is still trying to grasp what exactly that is.

My research into Gen Z habits and specific responses to humor will help companies and advertisers understand a demographic with a high potential to be a significant market of consumers. Building on an already solid framework, my specific questions and methods via primary research exploring advertising executions will continue to grow the canon of advertising humor tactics. With the age of social media, quick information, and short life spans of jokes and events via social media, a challenge must be faced to continue the industry and find significant success with humor. As an individual part of this demographic, I better understand what specific questions need to be asked and how the industry can use this research to expand on what has already been done before but mold the methods specifically for Gen Z. By constructing content that uses absurdist humor, intentionally creating bizarre

executions, and forgoing traditional humorous tropes, advertisements and advertising companies can achieve positive reactions from Gen Z consumers, ultimately gaining their attention, trust, and loyalty.

Literature Review

I. Humor And Advertising

Humor is a powerful strategic advertising appeal used across all industries and categories. Specifically, those in the advertising industry know how to reach their audience profoundly and intuitively effectively. A compelling message can be sent memorably to their target population with humor that successfully promotes both the product and the campaign. Humorous ads are more memorable in the minds of those exposed to the advertisement (Cline, T. W., & Kellaris, J. J., 2007). Though its effectiveness has been measured, in most instances, humor is not a one-size-fits-all methodology. It works only when utilized within a campaign or sole advertisement that can justify its usage. Spotts, Weinberger, and Parsons (1997) explain that using humor can be effective, but some variables can affect the campaign's success. Such variables include specific mechanisms, humor-relatedness, and the advertised product (p. 18). Humor is contextual and flexible, especially with multiple factors that can be manipulated. This literature review will examine the importance of humor in advertising and how these humorous advertisements aimed at Gen Z are essential when determining the advertising industry's future. Answering why companies have encountered difficulty with a very profitable demographic and how to help elevate that issue for intended success.

II. Why Humor?

Deceptiveness and Success

Humor rides a fine line between deceptive, practical, and successful to companies and brands worldwide. Thwaites and Shabbir (2007) investigate the concept of humor as a

masking device in advertising. A content analysis of 238 ads researched the ethics of humor and the types of deceptive claims found in certain ads (p. 83). Thwaites and Shabbir (2007) understand there is an unintentional deception alongside the intentional use of humor to sell a product with the tool masking negative perceptions. In comparison, Gulas and Weinberger (1992) concluded that humor does attract attention but does not seem to have an advantage or disadvantage over non-humor ads in the power of persuasion (p. 56). If the research that has been conducted on humor and advertising has been revealed to be somewhat neutral or negative, why do companies still use humor as a popular tool? Research conducted by Oracle Fusion Cloud Consumer Experience Happiness Report (Pastore, 2022) revealed that 94% of those surveyed in the Gen Z and Millennial groups said that they prefer when ads are humorous. Additionally, 90% said they are more likely to remember an advertisement they found funny (p. 21).

Responses To Humor

Despite possible negative perceptions or outcomes, companies want to use humor because that is what their target audience responds to. Karlovitch (2022) writes about insights from 12,000 consumers; nine out of 10 consumers prefer that brands use humor in their advertisements. Now, with the added factor of social media, the advertising efforts in comedy are beginning to revolve around digital media spaces.

According to the Advertising & Marketing Services - Quarterly Update (2022), there has been a significant increase in advertisers promoting digital spaces. Global advertising exceeded 55% in 2022 and is only projected to grow. Despite any negative concerns, the future of advertising looks heavily upon those already immersed in digital spaces and realms, such as Gen Z or Millennials. When an ad is aimed at a particular audience, all aspects will ensure it's relevant to them, even if the ad somewhat bets on their target audience to understand and immediately get the point. Humor is not universal or translated well outside

the realms of who they are aiming at. Despite all possible bad reactions or outcomes, the positive aspects of humor to companies outweigh the negative ones that can appear.

Consumers like to laugh, and companies are willing to comply.

Complexities of Specific Humor

Using humor and other tactics is becoming more complex and specific. As the generation after Millennials (1981-1996) becomes adults with incomes and buying habits, companies and brands are determined to market heavily to Gen Z's interests and generational quirks. There is a financial incentive to appeal to these consumers and find what they respond positively to. A recent Bank of America statement concluded that Gen Z's income will reach a predicted \$33 trillion by 2030 Montgomery (2021). However, when using hyper-specific humor that isn't quite right, the pitfalls of the tactics can be extremely apparent. These efforts by companies to target Gen Z will become ridiculed and mocked by their target audience. As explained by Fromm and Read (2018), the elusiveness of Gen Z is bringing extreme difficulty to companies trying to find what this generation responds to. If this generation is marketed poorly, aggressively, or sometimes even at all, the backlash from Gen Z is severe, and the company is seen as "try-hards." These adverse reactions are also visible and can spread quickly with the added factor of social media and its pervasiveness (p. 34).

Possible Solutions

Though challenging, as explained by Fromm and Read, this generation is not impossible to market towards. On their Tik-Tok account, the company Scrub Daddy boosted 1.8 million followers. Their described absurdist humor has caught the attention of Gen Z and successfully grown their company (Follett, 2022). There is still a level of difficulty and engagement within this population that has yet to be examined thoroughly or earnestly. Companies need to understand the complexities of Gen Z and how they can successfully

reach them, but there is an example with Scrub Daddy with generous returns. As researched and explained by Nurbasari et al. (2023):

The odd and surprising creative sensation displayed by the supporting role in the advertising scene generates a humorous response against the background of the theme of traditional cultural expressions so that it becomes an attraction and becomes viral and even trends on Instagram social media in Indonesia and abroad (p. 201).

Humor may affect both ad attitude and brand attitude to those who are viewing it. Through their research, Zhang (1996) believed that those with low cognition were more susceptible to being influenced by peripheral cues in humorous ads. In contrast, those with a high need for cognition were more likely to scrutinize the ad and brand (p. 12). Though high/low cognition is a possible explanation, it is not solely the reason why Gen Z is highly critical. The lack of Gen Z input and review, as Montgomery (2021) suggested, is why advertisements fail. Having actual target audience members may help reveal possible outcomes of said creative approaches.

III. Conclusion

Humor and Gen Z can go hand in hand if companies are willing to understand that they have to be the ones to take action and allow the generation to speak for themselves. Despite negative connotations, there is a definite appeal to using humor when there is authenticity behind it that the target generation can feel is genuine. Thus proving that humor can be used for longevity, but only when the consumers accept the appeal presented to them. Therefore, my research seeks to answer and explore why companies struggle with this specific audience using this particular tactic. There may be multiple reasons for lack of success, but those reasons have yet to be explored. Ask Gen Z themselves what works and doesn't work, and find long-term successful solutions that can benefit both Gen Z consumers and companies advertising towards them.

Methodology

The main research question in this study was: What are the significant requirements that make a successful Gen Z humorous advertisement? Questions also delved into understanding the usefulness of humor and Gen Z-specific quirks. As well as finding if there was anything that Gen Z consumers overwhelmingly do not like regarding humor advertisements they see today. My research wanted to understand better and, more specifically, how advertisers and companies can harness the tactic of humor and use the information to appeal to this specific age group with more efficacy.

To answer the questions related to Gen Z and humor, an online survey was created and published to understand consumers' thoughts, dislikes, and overall feelings within the Gen-Z demographic aged 18-26. The Qualtrics online survey was conducted from June 2023 to August 2023 and was solely spread through social media sites Instagram and Facebook. With the addition of the snowball effect, the number of participants reached 438 responses.

This survey method was chosen to get a more comprehensive data pool for more accurate responses that better reflect the group. Rather than conducting a smaller-scale study in person or with specific individuals, the survey was distributed online with easy access within three months. The study targeted individuals aged 18-26. However, because the survey was disseminated online, there was no way to ensure only this demographic was reached. Overall, even with this possible margin of error, the data collection succeeded, gaining better insights into the Gen Z demographic and their thoughts on humor and advertising.

With 17 questions in the survey, it took participants 10-15 minutes to complete with a mixture of qualitative and quantitative questions to better understand the participants' feelings. The survey included six short answer questions, nine multiple-choice questions, one ranking question, and one scale question. Eight questions were related to the four advertisements shown to participants: Burger King, Scrub Daddy, Hilton, and Duolingo. The

other nine questions were related to general feelings and thoughts about today's advertising landscape. The 17 questions aimed to probe a better understanding of the participants and their likes, dislikes, and any room for improvement in the advertisements they were given to analyze.

Results

Data analysis included statistical analysis and thematic qualitative analysis. Survey results suggested that Gen Z consumers wanted to see an improvement in advertising targeted towards their demographic. 174 participants overwhelmingly agreed that advertisements now lack creativity and are heading in an unhappy direction (e.g., annoying, lacking uniqueness, trying too hard.) (See Appendix A). Some of the themes that came up in the short answers were negative reservations about the promotions shown, general feelings about ads, and how humor is used in the modern advertising landscape. Many of the short answer questions reflected the thoughts of “When executed right” or “I don’t think they are funny” (See Appendix B and Appendix E). Overall, Gen Z's personal feelings are that they are looking for advertisements to improve, and many of the respondents wished for change.

The most successful ads out of the four brands shown to participants were the Scrub Daddy Tik-Tok advertisement and the Duolingo long-form advertisement on YouTube. 101 participants found that the cleaning supplies brand Scrub Daddy advertisement was extremely funny and 134 participants found it somewhat funny (Appendix C). For the language learning app-based company, Duolingo, advertisement, 113 participants found the ad extremely funny, while 99 found it somewhat funny (Appendix D).

Summary

In conclusion, data suggest that advertisements need to be *creative, authentic, and relevant*. *Creativity*: Gen Z wants to see an ad that they have never seen before creatively. Thinking outside the box of normal conventions and embracing the world of humor to its

fullest and wackiest extent. *Authenticity*: A number of the respondents expressed that they felt ads made using humor do not feel as if someone in their Gen Z demographic is making them but rather someone older. Companies not versed in Gen Z may need to learn precisely how a joke may be interpreted if the creators of that ad aren't in the generation they are targeting. This brings up the last theme: *Relevancy*. The two successful ads shown in the survey took advantage of trends and memes (internet-based inside jokes). The Scrub Daddy ad was posted to their Tik-Tok account, featuring a popular sound that users can remix and add their own context to. It was the shortest of the four advertisements and was made with Gen Z in mind, as TikTok has a larger Gen Z population than other social media apps. As for Duolingo, the advertisement took advantage of the growing number of memes surrounding their bird mascot being aggressive towards its users if they did not practice their daily language lessons. Both advertisements touched on popular trends and played along with their audience in a way that Burger King and Hilton advertisements did not. Using these three key themes, humor, and advertising can better their strategic approaches and the products being promoted.

Conclusion

Overall, the research has tapped into a market somewhat untouched by advertising. Understanding what appeals to Gen Z and makes them want to engage with a product or company can take time and effort. Humor had already been proven a great tactic (Pastore, 2022, pg . 21). However, the central point of contention and focus within the research was finding precisely what made that tactic appealing to this particular demographic. The answer to what makes a successful ad using humor is that it needs to contain *creativity, authenticity, and relevance*. Participants responded the most positively to advertisements outside of traditional, structured humor. *Creativity, authenticity, and relevance* were all aspects that participants wrote about and reflected in their choices during the survey. With those three key themes, advertisers using humor and tackling Gen Z consumers would hopefully have a better

success rate. Humor is subjective, but allowing a generation's quirks to shine through in advertisements would give companies and advertisers better engagement, recognition, and, of course, the target audience buying the product.

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Appendix**Appendix A (Question 9)**

Q9 - Do you feel advertisements now are lacking in creativity?

Appendix B (Question 10)

Q10 - What would you personally say is your general opinion of modern advertisements?

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What would you personally say is your general opinion of modern advertise...

at times, falling out of humor (dull humor)

Annoying lol

Faded in the background and mostly unremarkable

Most Modern Ads usually go the celebrity endorsement route and the pick people I don't care about to me personally

They can occasionally lack relativity to the product they are advertising

Appendix C (Question 11)

Scrub Daddy Advertisement

Q11 - Did you find this advertisement funny? Why or why not?

Appendix D (Question 12-Part 2)

Duolingo Advertisement

Q12-part2 - How funny did you find this advertisement?

Appendix E (Question 21)

Q21 - Lastly, what do think of advertisements that are trying to be funny?

Lastly, what do think of advertisements that are trying to be funny?

I am glad that they are trying to be funny because not everything had to be so serious

It depends on the delivery

They're more appealing when executed right.

Depends on each individual one. Most try too hard.

Trying to be funny is never funny bruh

I think it depends on how they are trying to be funny. Either way, it makes the ad more memorable.

They can be done right, but are hard to accomplish without being too corny. Ultimately, ads won't please every single person on Earth, and should mainly focus on the audience they're trying to relate to

I appreciate advertisements that try to be funny, because then it's not boring and I don't mind watching it.

When done well they are hilarious

If it's done incorrectly, I think the companies are trying too hard or they don't have a young person on their team that can provide valuable creative insights. If its done well, I my opinion of the company is higher and I see them as an entity that understands their publics and is actually in touch